

INFORMED CONSENT FORM (ICF) for protocol StrogHAT

Site Name/Site Number: _____

Principal Investigator Name: _____

Participant Identification Number for this trial: _____

Product Name Acoziborole

Protocol Title	An intervention study to evaluate the impact of treating gHAT seropositive subjects with acoziborole on transmission of <i>T.b. gambiense</i> , and obtain further safety data on acoziborole in gHAT seropositive individuals.
Short Title	Stop transmission of <i>gambiense</i> human African trypanosomiasis
Protocol Number/Version/Date	Amendment 1.0 of 11 July 2024 of the study protocol of 22 December 2023
Coordinating investigator	Dr Elena Nicco Institute of Tropical Medicine - Department of Public Health, Antwerp, Belgium
Study Part B Investigators	Dr-Dawili Ngosse Yannick Medical head of HAT HGR Karawa DRC Dr Petamoto Bbukilu Bienvenu Medical head of HAT team HGR Gemen DRC Dr. Yuma Dime Richard Medical head of HAT HGR Bwamanda DRC
Study Part B co-investigators	Dr. Kitshiaba Mukawa Michel Medical director HGR Gemena DRC Dr. Mokanda Dote Jacques Medical director HGR Karawa DRC Dr. NDANDA YADOWE Willy Medical director HGR Tandala DRC Dr. Nvula Koyambe Rodigue Medical director HGR Gbadolite DRC

	Dr. NGWELI – NGWELI Angèle DoctorHGR Bwamanda DRC
Study Coordinator and sponsor of study Part A	Institute of Tropical Medecine (ITM) Antwerp Belgium
Sponsor Study Part B	Drugs for Neglected Diseases initiative (DNDi) , Geneva, Switzerland

Introduction

You (your child) have/has been referred to/given an appointment with the study doctor because your/your child may have been in contact with the parasite responsible for sleeping sickness (also called Human African Trypanosomiasis, HAT). However, the parasite was not detected, and this situation needs to be followed as per national policy especially as you (your child) might be infected anyway. In that context, a new strategy (called screen and treat) to interrupt the transmission of sleeping sickness is being assessed and the doctor would like you (your child) to consider participating in a clinical study aiming to increase the knowledge of a new drug (acoziborole). This drug has not been approved yet in the treatment of HAT.

Before you decide whether to participate or not, it is important for you to read through this form to understand why the study is being done, what you (your child) will be asked to do and what are your (your child's) rights if you (your child) decide(s) to participate.

To help you to decide whether you want (or want your child) to take part in the study or not, please ask your doctor as many questions as you want to make sure that you clearly understand all words or procedures in this document and that you fully understand all that will happen in this study. You may also take the time to discuss the study with other people (relatives or friends) if you wish to do so.

Once you (your child) have (has) understood the explanation given in this form and all your questions have been answered to your satisfaction, if you (and your child) decide to participate in the clinical study, you will be asked to sign this form to confirm your (your child's) participation, (your child will be asked to sign an assent form) and you will be given a copy of this information.

Your decision to take part (your child) in this study is voluntary. That means that you (your child) can join this study if you want to, or not join if you (your child) do(es) not want to. Joining or not joining will not affect your (your child's) medical care

The research will:

- Determine whether the strategy tested can interrupt the transmission of sleeping sickness (study Part A)
- Contribute to increasing the knowledge of acoziborole, a new drug currently under development in the treatment of sleeping sickness (safety study Part B)
- Assess the cost of the strategy (Study Part A)
- Contribute to research new diagnostic tests (Study Part A)

Procedures performed in Study Part A are part of routine activities therefore no specific consent is required except for the use of data collected. The information provided in this document and the consent form deal with the study Part B and the additional samples to be taken at Month 4 for study Part A.

Who is sponsoring and funding the trial?

The sponsor oversees and manages the research study, collects and analyzes the trial data. In this research, the coordinator of the study is ITM (Institute of Tropical Medicine) Antwerp. DNDi (Drugs for Neglected Diseases initiative) is the organization that is developing acoziborole and is the sponsor of the safety study (study Part B). The funder is the organization that pays for the trial. In this trial, the funder is EDCTP (European and Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership)

What is the treatment I (my child) will receive?

If you (your child) are (is) eligible to the safety study and you agree to participate in (your child participates in), you (your child) will receive acoziborole. Acoziborole is a new drug that is being tested for the treatment of HAT that is not yet approved by Health Authorities (government authorities).

If you are (your child is) 15 years old or over, you (your child) will receive 3 tablets of 320 mg each of acoziborole to be swallowed in a single intake.

If your child is between 11 and 14 years old and weighs over 30kg, she/he will receive 2 tablets of 320 mg of acoziborole to be swallowed in a single intake.

If you are (your child is) not eligible to the study or if you are (your child is) eligible but you (your child) refuse(s) to take part, you (your child) will receive standard of care as per national treatment guidelines.

Which procedures will be done to me during the study?

The procedures that will be done during the safety study are described below .

- **Medical History:** The trial staff will ask you about your (your child's) health and about any previous medical problems, operation or allergies
- **Medicines:** The trial staff will ask you about any medicines you (your child) have (has) been or are (is) currently taking. It could be dangerous to your health if you do not list all medicines, supplements, traditional remedies etc that you (your child) are (is) taking. Depending on the treatments you are taking, you may not be able to participate in this study.
- **Clinical examination:** The study staff will thoroughly examine you (your child) to see if you (your child) have (has) no medical condition preventing your participation into the study. The trial staff will also measure your (your child's) height, weight, temperature, blood pressure and heart rate. At each visit, the trial staff will check your (your child's) health.
- **Urine sampling (for women of childbearing potential only):** we will collect your (your daughter's) urine at minimum 2 times during the study (at screening, and month 4) to check for pregnancy. The study staff might ask for some additional pregnancy tests in case of suspicion of pregnancy during the study. The following total volume of urine will be withdrawn: 30 mL (~ 6 teaspoon)

If you (your child) are (is) eligible to the study treatment, you (your child) will receive acoziborole within 5 days.

Between 3 to 8 days after you (your child) have (has) taken the study treatment, the study staff will visit you (your child) at your home or you (your child) will go the study site for the following assessments:

- **Adverse events:** you (your child) will be asked how you (she/he) feel(s) by the trial doctor/trial nurse to assess any possible health conditions and side effects related or not to the study treatment
- **Concomitant medications:** the trial staff will ask you (your child) about any medicines, including traditional one you (your child) are (is) currently taking. If you (your child) are/is taking some medicine that may interact with Acoziborole, you (your child) will have to be taken out of the study. the study. You (your child) must not take any medicine without prior approval of the study doctor.

Four months after you (your child) have (has) taken the study treatment (with a window period of – 10 days to + 1 month post-treatment), you (your child) will be asked to go to the clinical site/receive an home visit, to perform the clinical assessment, the urine sampling (for women of child bearing potential only), the adverse events and the concomitant medication. In addition, if you (your child) were (was) positive to one of the immunological or molecular test done during the routine procedure, blood sampling of 6 mL (about 1 teaspoon) will be collected for immunological tests and molecular tests. If judged necessary to your health, the study doctor may take some additional blood samplings.

What are the foreseen risks and inconveniences associated with the study procedures?

Samplings are normal routine procedures which are also used by the national control program (PNLTHA) during their assessment. The medical team will do their best to minimize any possible discomfort or harm to you (your child). The blood collection will be done by experts and any infection that may arise because of this will be treated. Blood will be taken from your elbow crease by using a thin needle. You (your child) may feel a slight pain where the needle is inserted. The amount of blood taken is too small to affect your health.

How will my samples be used?

The urine samples collected of women of childbearing potential will be analysed directly in the clinical site/at your home and not stored. Blood samples collected as part of the research will be sent to the below reference laboratories: INRB (Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of Congo) and ITM (Belgium, Europe) and IRD (Montpellier, France) for specific disease tests and may be used for further research.

No genetic testing will be done.

You can indicate whether or not you agree with this research or any future research in Part 2 of this document. Even if you decide that you do not want us to store your blood samples, you can still participate in the study.

Your samples will not be sold or used for any commercial purposes.

Inconveniences

As a participant, your/your child will have to adhere to study schedule and procedures.

What are the foreseen risks and inconveniences associated with the study treatment?

During the safety study, you (your child) will be followed closely at the planned visits or anytime if judged necessary by you or the study staff. Contact details are given at the end of this document. Like any other drug, it is possible that acoziborole causes some problems that DNDi is not aware of. Any problem or unwanted effect will be notified to DNDi, and the appropriate care will be provided.

Acoziborole is a new treatment and can't be found in any pharmacy, but previous clinical trials have been conducted by the DNDI where about 1245 individuals already received a single dose of acoziborole.

A few unwanted events were reported and most of them were mild to moderate. As far as we know today, the type of unwanted effects associated with acoziborole that you (your child) might encounter include abdominal pain, headaches, feeling hot, vomiting, tiredness, and decrease of appetite. In most cases, these unwanted effects lasted 24 hours and appear within the 5 days following the intake of acoziborole

As some interactions with other drugs have been noticed, you must avoid taking any additional medicines without prior consultation with your investigating doctor or herbal or natural therapeutic products during the 4 months of your participation in the study, i.e. during the 4 months immediately after taking acoziborole.

During the study, if you have a health problem, we advise you to contact the study's investigating doctor, who may prescribe medication for you after medical consultation.

A group of independent professionals will monitor the safety of acoziborole and they can stop the study for safety reason. If this should happen, you will be notified rapidly and the monitoring of your (your child's) health will be continued.

How many people will participate? How long will the study last?

The study will be conducted in DRC, in the DPS of Nord Ubangi, Sud Ubangi and Mongala. We expect about 2500 inclusions in 3 years of recruitment.

In total, your participation in the safety study will last about 4 months. The total duration of the research study is 4 years.

What would be my (my child) responsibilities if I (my child) participate(s) in the study?

You (your child) must strictly comply with the study requirements described in this document and follow all the recommendations given by the study staff. It is listed in part 2.

For women of childbearing potential:

Because DNDi, the Sponsor, does not have sufficient data on the effect of acoziborole on the development of a baby, as a precautionary measure we consider that the treatment might harm the unborn child. If you (and your child) decide to participate in this study, you (your daughter) will have to:

- Accept to have pregnancy tests done before taking part in the study, and at 4 months after you (your daughter) received the study drug.
- Agree to use an appropriate contraceptive method to avoid becoming pregnant from the signature of this consent form up to 3 months after you (your daughter) have (has) received the study medication. If you wish to continue taking contraception after 3 months, because of the risk of drug interactions with acoziborole and the risk of lack of efficacy of hormonal contraception, we recommend that you use a barrier method for a further month (i.e. up to 4 months after taking acoziborole). The site medical staff will advise you (your daughter) about the most adapted contraceptive methods (, condoms or else hormonal contraceptives). Acoziborole may interact with hormonal contraceptives, and reduce the efficacy of this contraception method after 3 months. If you continue hormonal contraception after 3 months, you (your daughter) will be advised to use condoms in addition to hormonal contraception up to 4 months after acoziborole. These condoms and hormonal contraceptives will be provided free of charge to you (your daughter).

If pregnancy is detected during the study participation, you (your daughter) must tell your study doctor **immediately**, so appropriate action and arrangements can be discussed with you (your daughter) regarding the monitoring of the pregnancy, assistance at delivery, and monitoring of the health of the future baby until 2 years of age. In case of abnormality, an appropriate follow-up will be offered to you (your daughter). The study sponsors may also request your (and your daughter's) consent to collect confidential information about your (your daughter's) health and the health of your (her) baby until it reaches 2 years of age.

What would be the benefits to participate in the study?

- No direct benefit can be expected but you (your child) will receive medical care and be monitored closely during the trial and if the study treatment is not effective, you (your child) will receive the current standard treatment for your condition.
- All examinations, medications, and medical care during the study will be provided free of charge.

- The Sponsor will arrange and pay for transportation to the study site and back. The study site will be as close to your home as possible.
- Lastly, the results from the data collected during the study might help researchers to improve the diagnosis and the treatment of people suspected of sleeping sickness and help to interrupt the transmission of this disease from your country.

What are the alternatives if I do not want (my child) to take part in the study (if my child does not want to take part in the study)?

Your (your child's) participation in this study is voluntary. If the decision is not to take part in the safety study, a follow-up will be proposed according to national guidelines from the PNLTHA. The PNLTHA will ask you (your child) to attend regular visits to health facilities/during mobile units activities, for examinations to ensure that the appropriate treatment is provided if you (your child) develop(s) the disease.

You (your child) can change your (her/his) decision at any time during the study without losing any of your (her/his) rights or having to give a reason. This will not impact your relationship with the Trial Doctor. In this case the procedure of the PNLTHA will be applied to ensure that medical care is provided.

During the course of a clinical study, new information may become available about the study medication. If this happens the Study Doctor will inform you (your child) about it and will discuss the continuation of the study. If the decision is to stop the participation in the safety study, the study doctor will make arrangements for your (your child's) care to continue. The data collected until your (your child's) withdrawal will be kept and used for the study.

It is also possible that the study doctor, health authorities or the study sponsors may decide to withdraw you (your child) from the trial if it is believed this is in your (your child's) best interests. In this case, information will be shared with you and the study doctor will ensure that medical care you (your child) need(s) is provided. Any new data collected for the study and all information and samples collected until the withdrawal will be kept.

Research involving people is strictly regulated by laws in the field of public health. These laws mandate the sponsor to ensure your (your child's) safety and the integrity of the results of the trial. The Sponsor is also obliged to keep your (your child's) information for many years, at least 25 years after the end of the trial or even longer if the drug is put on the market. This is mandated by law and is necessary in the public interest.

If you (your child) withdraw your consent from the safety study and object to the use of your (your child's) information from that timepoint, the study sponsors will stop collecting new information, but the study sponsors will not be able to stop all activities with data already collected to comply with the study sponsors's legal and ethical obligations.

What will be the personal information of mine that will be processed?

We collect and use information about your (your child's) personal data out of the study sponsor legitimate interest to answer scientific questions and to support the approval and medical use of acoziborole for the interruption of transmission of sleeping sickness. The study sponsor can do more research to try to further improve the health and care of people affected by sleeping sickness or similar disease. This cannot be done without using your information. The Study Doctor and research team will collect your (your child's) personal information on behalf and under the authority of the study sponsor.

The type of personal information which will be collected includes:

- Your (your child's) personal details: name, address, telephone number, age, gender, etc.
- Your (your child's) medical history including all medications currently being taken.

- Information collected as a result of study examination and procedures
- If you are a women and you (your daughter) become(s) pregnant during the study period, the study sponsor will also collect information about your (daughter's) pregnancy, delivery and your (her) child up to 2 years.

Will my personal data remain confidential?

Your (your child's) identity, data in your (your child's) medical records, data resulting from the biological samples and your (your child's) participation in this research will be strictly confidential. Your (your child's) identifying personal data, such as your (your child's) name and contact details, will only be kept at the site. Before it is transferred out of the site, your (your child's) identifying personal data will be removed and replaced by a code so that only the site trial personnel will know that you (your child) participated in the trial as well as a limited authorized persons (such as monitors, auditors, ethics committees) to ensure that the trial is being conducted correctly.

Your (your child's) identifying personal data might also have to be shared with one or more national regulatory authorities if requested by them, or to comply with the law. In exceptional circumstances when required due to safety concerns or to investigate potential fraud, your (your child's) identifying personal data may be disclosed to the sponsor and other individuals authorized by the sponsor (such as the insurance representatives).

Your (your child's) coded personal data, i.e. identified by your (your child's) trial number, will be sent to ITM, DNDi, associated partners, funders and third parties acting on their behalf for this research.

Except the PNLTHA who is involved in routine activities or care linked to this research, nobody will have any data that identifies you (your child) personally.

The persons and organizations that will receive your (your child's) de-identified data will be subject to confidentiality rules in accordance with the applicable regulatory requirement(s) or will be obliged by the contract to protect the confidentiality and security of your (your child's) personal data.

In addition, for activities which may involve higher risks (for example, data transfer), sponsor will apply additional protection, such as encryption. Encryption is the process of encoding a message or information in such a way that only authorized parties can read it and those who are not authorized cannot.

Your (your child's) de-identified data will be processed within and outside your country including at minimum Belgium, France, Switzerland, Kenya. Some of these countries may not provide adequate level of protection of personal data, such as Kenya. The study sponsors will ensure that adequate safeguards, contractual and technical, are in place for transfers to these countries. If you require information on where your data will be transferred and under what conditions, please contact the trial site.

At the end of the trial, a report will be written about the results of the trial; however any publication of the trial results (this report or any derived publications) will not include your (your child's) identifying personal data. A description of this research trial will be available on publicly accessible database or registries. These websites will not include information that can identify you (your child). At most, the website will include a summary of the results and you can search this website at any time.

You have the right to access and correct or request the erasure of your data at any time, however these rights might be limited due to other requirements and will be decided on a case-by-case basis. While we are treating your request, you have the right to ask for suspension of the processing of your data.

Your (your child's) de-identified coded personal data will also be used for the research conducted by ITM or other organisations for additional not yet defined research purposes and may be combined with other databases for such purposes.

DNDi (based in Switzerland), is responsible for the processing of your (your child's) personal data for this safety study. However, to exercise your (your child's) rights, for questions regarding how your (your child's) personal information is handled, please contact your study doctor in the first instance who knows your identity. DNDi will only receive your encoded data.

You can also contact DNDi's Data Protection Officer (DPO) at dataprivacy@dndi.org for any general questions during or after the safety study completion. It is to be noted that the sponsor's DPO may not be able to answer all questions because they only have access to your (your child's) coded data and do not know your (your child's) identity. As DNDi is located outside of the EU, DNDi has designated the EU Data Protection Representative as the EU Data Protection Representative.

How will I be compensated in case of study related injury?

The sponsor has obtained insurance for the study participants in the event of a study-related injury or illness. If this would happen, the sponsor will pay for all medical care or damage suffered.

A representative of the insurance company may request access to your (your child's) confidential data in the event of a claim.

What happens if another medical condition is found as a result of the tests done during this trial?

During this trial, as a result of the tests performed, previously undiagnosed medical conditions could be discovered (called incidental findings).

If found, the Trial Doctor will inform you (and your child) and refer you (your child) to an appropriate service or practitioner who will look after you (your child). Neither the sponsor nor the Study Doctor are responsible for confirming the incidental findings, nor are obliged to provide medical advice or opinion or to be responsible for any subsequent health care decisions based on the findings.

Who should I contact if I have a question related to the study?

Call immediately the study doctor or caregivers if at any time you feel sick. Contact details are given in page 1 of this document.

This safety study and all associated documents have been reviewed and approved by the Institute Review Board of ITM, the Ethics Committee of the University of Antwerp Hospital in Antwerp and the National Ethic Committee of DRC to make sure that the rights, safety, and well-being of the participants will be protected.

If you have any questions about the study, in case of study-related injury, or if you experience any event that requires medical care during the study, you can contact your study doctor:

Name: Dr.

Telephone:

Or one of the study co-investigators:

Name : Dr.

Name : Dr.

Telephone :

Telephone :

You will be given a copy of this information sheet along with the part 2: consent/assent form.

Site Number: |__|__|

Participant Identification Number : |__|__|__|__|__|__|

Information sheet for children ≥ 11 years old

Study Title: An intervention study to evaluate the impact of treating gHAT seropositives subjects with acoziborole on transmission of T.b. gambiense, and obtain further safety data on acoziborole in gHAT seropositives individuals

Name of Sponsor: Drugs for Neglected Diseases *initiative* (DNDi), Chemin Camille-Vidart 15, 1202 Geneva, Switzerland.

Purpose of the study: You are here because you may have been in contact with the parasite that transmits a disease called the sleeping sickness. Even if the parasite has not been found in your body, you can still be infected and be infective. Researchers are testing new ways to fight the disease with a new drug called acoziborole.

What will I have to do? The study doctor will examine you and ask you questions about your health and the medications you take. You must not take any medication without telling your study doctor. If your participation is possible and you agree to participate in this project, you will take a new drug (2 or 3 pills) one single time. About 3 days later, a nurse will visit you to check if you are feeling good. After about 4 months, you will come for a last visit. If the doctor thinks you may have the sleeping sickness, the doctor will take some about 1 teaspoon of blood from your arm to verify if you have the disease and to make sure you receive the right treatment. Your blood will be sent to researchers.

If you are a girl in age of childbearing, the doctor will ask you to take precautions to avoid becoming pregnant in the 4 months following treatment. You are asked to bring some urine (about 6 teaspoons) at the study visits to be sure you are not expecting a baby. Your urine will not be kept. Despite all the precautions if you are a girl and you become pregnant during the study, the study doctor will follow-up your pregnancy and your future baby until your baby is 2 years old to check you and your baby are in good health. The information on your pregnancy and on your baby will be transmitted to the sponsor, researchers and to competent authorities but neither your identity nor the one of your baby will be disclosed. In case of abnormalities, you will be offered an appropriate follow-up.

Is that painful? The blood sampling can be painful, but the study team will do his maximum to not hurt you and this is not dangerous for your health.

Can I refuse? You can refuse to participate in this study or only refuse the study doctor to take your blood and you can withdraw from the study at any time without any problems. You will receive treatment if you need some. All your information and your examinations will be kept by the researchers until the day of your refusal and can be used for future research or be shared with other people. Only the study team will know your name.

Site Number: |_|_|_|

Participant Identification Number : |_|_|_|_|_|_|_|_|_|

PART 2 CONSENT/ASSENT FORM

Title of Project: Stop transmission of *gambiense* human African trypanosomiasis

STROGHAT- study

The study has been approved by the ethics committee of your country.

I have read the information in this form, or it has been read to me in a language that I understand well. I have had the opportunity to discuss with the study doctor about it, ask all the questions I had and received satisfying answers.

By signing this document, I understand:

1. That my (child's) participation is completely voluntary, and I (my child) can refuse to participate in the study without penalty or loss of benefits to which I (my child) would have been otherwise entitled.
2. That if I (my child) agree(s) to participate, I (my child) can withdraw at any time without losing benefits or services to which I (my child) or my family are entitled.
3. That if I (my child) withdraw(s) my (her/his) consent to participate in this trial, the Sponsor will keep and process any samples and data collected up to the point of my (her/his) withdrawal.
4. That if I (my child) is at risk of g-HAT, an additional blood sample might be taken at M4
5. That my (child's) leftover and additional samples and associated data may be further used for additional/future research purposes and I (my child) agree(s) to this use.
6. That my (child's) de-identified coded data collected during the study will be used for the need of the study and for future research following the approval of the Ethic Committees and Health authority.
7. That my (child's) personal data can be accessible to authorized personnel (doctor and clinical staff) as well as representatives of the sponsor (monitors, audit personnel, etc.) and ethics committees and national health authorities' representatives.
8. That my (child's) personal data may be transferred abroad, including Switzerland, France, Belgium, Kenya. I understand that this trial cannot be done without such a transfer and I (my child) do(es) not object to it.
9. That I (my child) will respect the planning of the study and stay in contact with the study site personnel.
10. That I (my child) will not take part in any other clinical trials during my (her/his) participation in this study.
11. That no concomitant medication will be taken without the approval of the study doctor during the study duration.
12. That should any analysis/es reveal results not directly related to this trial, I agree to be informed.
13. That I (my daughter) must agree to take contraceptive measures during the study to not become pregnant and that in case of incidental pregnancy during the study, my (my daughter's) child will be followed and data collected, proceed and used until she/he reaches 2 years of age.

I have been informed about my rights and responsibilities during my study participation and I understand the purpose and the way my personal data and information will be used.

- I agree to participate in the part B of the trial Yes No
- I agree for my child/ward to participate in the part B of the trial Yes No
- I agree for the supplementary blood sampling at M4 if I am/my child is at risk of g-HAT Yes No
- I agree (my daughter) to take contraceptive measures during the study to not become pregnant and that in case of incidental pregnancy during the study, my (my daughter's) child will be followed, and data collected, proceed and used until she/he reaches 2 years of age Yes No
- I agree my (child's) leftover and additional samples and associated data may be further used for additional/future research purposes and I (my child) agree(s) to this use Yes No

Participant signature:

Date:

|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|
(dd/mmm/yyyy)

Or legal representative, guardian of the participants signature:

Date:

|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|
(dd/mmm/yyyy)

FOR ILLITERATE PARTICIPANTS AND/OR IN CASE OF ORAL TRANSLATION:

Should the patient be illiterate, or an oral translation is needed, the presence of an impartial witness is required throughout the entire consent procedure.

Witness signature (if required):

Date:

|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|
(dd/mmm/yyyy)

Translator signature:

Date:

|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|
(dd/mmm/yyyy)

For ASSENT

As the assent I have had chance to read or someone has read to me the information in this form and the study has been explained to me in the language I understand. I have been able to ask all the questions I want to and my questions have been answered.

I know I do not have to take part in the study and that I can change my mind during the study if I want to. I know that if I don't take part in the study I will still receive treatment.

ASSENT signature :

Date:

|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|
(dd/mmm/yyyy)

Name of the Investigator :

Dr.

Investigator signature:

Date:

|_|_|/|_|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|
(dd/mmm/yyyy)